

A platform for generating and training 3D skeletal muscle tissues *in vitro*

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Introduction

A simple platform has been developed for generating skeletal muscle tissues, which can potentially be used as a model to predict changes in structural composition and the resulting change in force-generation capacity of the tissue over large time scales e.g., > 20 days. This is done by culturing C2C12 myoblasts mixed with fibrin in flexible PDMS chambers with cantilevers on both sides that serve as attachment sites when the tissue compacts[1, 2]. With cantilevers of different sizes, the resistant forces between these cantilevers may vary. This could potentially lead to differences in tissue development. By analyzing cantilever deformation, cell alignment and proteins that indicate the maturation of the tissue, this platform allows us to study the resistive force generated by the cells and the effect of the boundary conditions during tissue development in a highly controlled environment.

Materials and Methods

The PDMS-based culture chamber consists of a cantilever on each side and it was laser-cut into the desired shape. The chambers were cleaned with ethanol and dried with air before transferring them to the tissue culture laminar hood. Before adding cells to the chambers, they were incubated in PBS overnight and primed with plain DMEM medium for at least one day. C2C12 myoblasts were cultured in proliferation medium and harvested before they reached full confluency. The desired number of cells were resuspended with plain DMEM medium, thrombin and CaCl₂. Then, fibrinogen was added to the mixture and the solution was transferred to the chamber immediately. The final cell density achieved was 10⁷ cells/ml. Then, the cell-gel mix was incubated at 37 °C and in 5% CO₂ for an hour to form the gel. Differentiation medium supplemented with 10 µg/mL aprotinin was added and changed every two days. Images were taken on several time points for cantilever bending angle analysis (Figs 1-2). Tissues were fixed and stained for cell alignment and protein expression analysis.

Results and Discussion

The size of the cantilever should provide the resistant force while the tissue compacts, at the same time it should allow viable fabrication in the lab. Several cantilever conditions were tested in the lab. In situations with no cantilevers presented, tissues compacted isotopically (Fig. 1a). With 3 mm-wide cantilevers, tissues compacted and caused bending of the cantilevers (Fig. 1b). When cantilever width was ≥ 5 mm, there was no deformation of the cantilever caused by the tissue compaction observed in the lab (Fig. 1c). Tissue development and maturation was studied by analyzing the relationship between the resistive forces provided by the cantilevers and the resulting cellular alignment as well as protein expressions (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Tissue compaction across different cantilever bending conditions. a) No cantilevers, b) 0.3 mm wide cantilevers and c) 0.5 mm wide cantilevers.

Figure 2. a) Cantilever bending due to the cellular forces generated overtime. b) Bending angle of the cantilevers changed over time and plateaued at day 5.

References

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